

R code for Principal Component Analysis and Hierarchical clustering

```
pca = prcomp(data, center=T, scale=T) # PCA
loadings = pca$x[]
x = loadings[,1]
y = loadings[,2]
z = loadings[,3]
dataPCA = cbind(x,y,z)
clust = hclust(dist(dataPCA, 'euclidean'), method = 'ward.D2')
plot(clust, axes=F,xlab="", ylab="",sub =", main='Comp 1/2/3')
clusterCut <- cutree(clust, 9) # 9 – number of clusters
table = mutate(data, cluster = clusterCut) # to add clusters to the original data to map it later
```